

A Note on the Photochemical Reaction between Ethylene Iodide and Iodine in Carbon Tetrachloride Solution.

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Schumacher and Wiig (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **B**, 11, 45) represent the course of the above reactions as follows:

and draw some interesting conclusions therefrom.

The decomposition of ethylene iodide should thus proceed from collisions between iodine atoms and ethylene iodide molecules. Now if the mechanism of reaction (iv) is ascertained, the total number of collisions between reacting bodies may easily be calculated. From a comparison of the total number of collisions with the number of effective collisions yielded by a study of the reaction kinetics, one is in a position to estimate the energy of activation (E). A second measure of E is given by the variation of the velocity of appearance of iodine (K) with temperature, for, this would be the only process involving activation by collision. Any agreement between the two values of E would give striking confirmation not only of the decomposition scheme assumed by Schumacher and Wiig, but also of the mechanism postulated for the union of the atoms of iodine.

From an inspection of the reaction [scheme it is obvious that the velocity constant (K) for the formation of iodine is given by

$$K = k_2 \sqrt{\frac{2I_{abs}}{k_4}} \cdot [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{I}_2]$$

where I_{abs} represents the energy absorbed by the reaction system per second per c.c. Of these quantities, K and I_{abs} are experimentally determinable and k_2 is known when a suitable value has been assigned to k_4 . The value of k_4 depends solely on the mechanism assumed for reaction (iv). Alternatively k_2 may be estimated from a consider-

ation of the collision-frequency and a knowledge of the heat of activation (E).

Schumacher and Wiig postulate that one in every five collisions between iodine atoms in the presence of a solvent molecule, results in the formation of a molecule of iodine and deduce a value for k_2 which is 32 times of that arrived at from considerations of the temperature coefficient data. This low efficiency factor $1/32$ for collisions between iodine atoms and ethylene iodide molecules is traced to the probable high steric factor, which the complexity of the iodide molecule is likely to bring to play.

While this argument is not wholly convincing, we have been led in our studies on the photosensitising action of iodine (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1934, **B**, 26, 255) to assume an efficiency of unity for the collisions of iodine atoms in the presence of a solvent molecule. We have, therefore, in the following examined the data of Schumacher and Wiig in the light of our data and found that the concept of a steric factor may completely be dispensed with in such reactions.

On this basis, we proceed to calculate Z_1 , the total number of collisions between iodine atoms and iodide molecules and by comparing this number with the number Z_2 , which represents the number of such collisions resulting in reaction, we obtain E . Thus

$$Z_2/Z_1 = e^{-E/RT}$$

Now Z_1 is given by the expression,

$$2\sqrt{2\pi} \cdot a^2 \cdot \sqrt{RT} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_1 + M_2}{M_1 M_2}} \cdot n \cdot n_e$$

where n is the number of iodine atoms per c.c., n_e , the number of iodide molecules per c.c., M , the mass of iodine atom, M_e , the mass of the iodide molecule, T , the temperature of the reaction, and a , the distance of nearest approach for reaction, of the centres of the iodide molecules and iodine atoms.

In this expression M , M_e , N_e and T are known. a is presumably equal to $\frac{1}{2}(S + S_1)$, where S and S_1 represent the diameters of the iodine atoms and iodide molecules respectively. $S = 2.72 \times 10^{-6}$ cm. (Landolt, "Tabellen," Part I, p. 38). Unfortunately S_1 is not known so definitely: but in such cases not much error is introduced by assuming a round figure of 5×10^{-8} cm. ("The Kinetics of Reactions in Solutions," p. 15). Thus, $a = 4.0 \times 10^{-8}$ cm. The only unknown then is n . This quantity may be determined as follows.

The number of iodine atoms per c.c. at the stationary state.—
On the basis that every binary collision of iodine atoms in the presence of a solvent molecule results in the formation of a molecule of iodine, the number of iodine molecules (N) appearing in unit volume in unit time is equal to

$$k_4 [I]^2 \cdot \frac{k'N_e}{1/\tau + k'N_e}$$

where N_e is the number of molecules per c.c. of the solvent and τ , the life-period of the iodine atom. Since the magnitude of N_e is so much greater than that of $1/\tau$, the fraction $\frac{k'N_e}{1/\tau + k'N_e}$ reduces to unity; and

$$N = k_4 [I]^2$$

and $[I]$ at the stationary state is given by $\sqrt{\frac{2I_{abs}}{h\nu \cdot k_4}}$. Thus

$$N = k_4 [I]^2 = k_4 \left[\sqrt{\frac{2I_{abs}}{h\nu \cdot k_4}} \right]^2 = \frac{2I_{abs}}{h\nu}$$

Now the number N is obviously equal to the number of collisions between iodine atoms per sec. per c.c.

$$= \sqrt{2} \cdot \pi \cdot S^2 \cdot u \cdot n^2$$

where S as before is the diameter of the neutral iodine atom and u , the *r. m. s.* velocity at the reaction temperature. Thus

$$\frac{2I_{abs}}{h\nu} = N = \sqrt{2} \cdot \pi \cdot S^2 \cdot u \cdot n^2$$

$$\text{and } n = \sqrt{\frac{2I_{abs}}{h\nu \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \pi \cdot S^2 \cdot u}}$$

Therefore $Z_1 = a^2 \sqrt{\left\{ 8\pi RT \left(\frac{1}{M_1} + \frac{1}{M_2} \right) \right\}} \cdot n \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2I_{abs}}{h\nu \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \pi \cdot S^2 \cdot u}}$

Substituting in this expression for the various quantities from Schumacher's data,

$$a = 4.0 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm. ; } T = 100^\circ = 373^\circ \text{ Abs. ; } M_1 = 127; M_2 = 280 ;$$

$$n_e = \frac{0.088 \times 6.06 \times 10^{23}}{1000}; \quad I_{abs} = \frac{1.97 \times 10^{15}}{55} \text{ Quanta per c.c.};$$

$$n = 2.70 \times 10^4 \text{ cm. per sec.}; \quad S = 2.72 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm.}$$

Z_1 becomes equal to 1.04×10^{22} per c.c. per sec. and $Z_2 = 9.0 \times 10^{14}$ per c.c. per sec. Then,

$$\frac{Z_2}{Z_1} = e^{-E/RT} = \frac{9.0 \times 10^{14}}{1.04 \times 10^{22}} = 8.65 \times 10^{-8}$$

$$\text{or } E = 12.0 \text{ Cals.}$$

This value of 12.0 Cals. for E is in excellent agreement with that of 11.8 Cals. given by Schumacher and Wiig. We are aware of the fact that our estimate of the diameter of ethylene iodide molecule is subject to a large error. A simple calculation shows, however, that within wide limits ($a = 1 \times 10^{-8}$ to 1.0×10^{-7} cm.), the value of E varies only from 11.5 to 12.2 Cals.

SUMMARY.

Schumacher and Wiig's postulate that only one in five of the binary collisions between iodine atoms results in molecule formation, has been shown to be incorrect from their data on this reaction. On the other hand the evidence is very much in favour of the hypothesis put forward by us that every such collision does lead to molecule formation. The energy of reaction has been calculated on this basis and shown to agree very well with that observed.

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